

‘BLESSING’ IN THE EXERCISE OF AUTHORITY

Dr. Lancy MONTEIRO SJ

The author <lanmonsj@gmail.com> has a doctorate in systematic theology from the Gregorian University, Rome. Presently, he teaches systematic theology in Jnana Deepa, Pune. He has written in some national and international journals.

Abstract: Authority may be used to serve personal interests, plan, ideology, vision, etc. In the Church, however, authority ought to be used to serve God-revealed eschatological vision, namely the ‘new heavens and new earth.’ This article elaborates the point that the eschatological vision is actually restoration of creation to its original state, which corresponded to God’s mind and heart and which God confirmed with acts of ‘blessing,’ and suggests that the Church needs to exercise authority to realize this eschatological vision, which is restoration of creation to its original state that God had confirmed with God’s act of blessing.

Keywords: Authority, Eschatological Vision, Blessing, Church.

INTRODUCTION

Authority is a fundamental aspect of human experience, present throughout every stage of life – childhood, adolescence, adulthood, and old age – and across all domains, including social, religious, political, and economic spheres. We encounter it both as recipients of its influence and as individuals empowered to exercise it. The Church, understood as the ‘people of God,’ the ‘body of Christ,’ and the ‘temple of the Holy Spirit,’ is no exception to this dynamic. Within the Church, authority is both exercised by its members and experienced by them. Generally, this exercise and reception of authority serves

the Church's life and mission, grounded in the teachings of Christ and his apostles.

However, might we also consider integrating the concept of 'blessing' – as introduced in the Genesis creation narrative – into our understanding of authority? Could this enrich and deepen the Church's mission and life? This essay explores that possibility. It begins by offering key clarifications, examines the sources and types of authority within the Church, and ultimately proposes 'blessing' – defined as actions that reflect and affirm God's will and heart – as a guiding vision for how authority might be exercised in ecclesial contexts.¹

1. AUTHORITY AS STANDING/POSITION IN SOCIETY

Derived from the Latin word '*auctoritas*,' the word authority originally referred to the influence which one wielded because of one's personal integrity, credibility, caliber, competence, moral weightiness in the society.² Authority may flow from one's competence, capabilities, legacy, etc., but more important in wielding authority is personal integrity, credibility, and moral weightiness. Precisely, authority that flows from one's standing in the society due to the latter factors mentioned commands more than the authority that flows from the former factors. For instance, a village leader commands not only because he/she is a leader and has authority, but also because of the integrity, credibility, and moral weightiness that might have taken him/her to the position of a leader. M. K. Gandhi commanded authority and respect not because of his physical strength, talents, academic qualification, but because of his personal integrity, credibility, and moral weightiness. The Roman Senate (a council/an advisory body) comprised of leading citizens of

¹ This essay was initially crafted as a talk intended for a lay audience, drawing upon a selection of existing written sources. Much of the material presented is borrowed from the scholars, except for the unique emphasis placed on the concept of 'blessing.'

² Cf. T. A. Lacey D.D., *Authority in the Church: A Study of Principles* (London: A.R. Mowbray & Co, 1928), 1f.

personal and moral integrity, who would advise legislature/magistracy and their advice/opinion almost had the effect of law, a binding force. Later on, the emperor Augustus in 27 BCE would build a new system called *Principate* to concentrate all authority in himself and exercise it. Nevertheless, the meaning of authority as influence one wields because of the position one holds in the society/empire would remain. One may remember here the words of Pilate, who exercised authority on behalf of the emperor, to Jesus – “Do you not know that I have authority/power to crucify you or release you?” (Jn 19:10). Diverse dictionaries would define the term ‘authority’ in the same manner, i.e., as the power or right to give commands, enforce obedience, take actions, or make final decisions due to the position one holds in the society.

2. A BINDING INTERACTION

David Stagaman sees authority as something that binds two individuals/parties: “Authority is an interaction which binds together at least two persons, one who has assumed an obligation and another who is acknowledged as being able to act on that obligation.”³ Some instances that we can think of are of Teacher–Student, Coach–Players, Employer–Employee. One possesses certain skills and imparts, and the other learns. It involves certain communication, responsibility.

3. AN AUTHORITY & IN AUTHORITY

Distinction is always made between an authority and in authority. When authority flows from the possession of certain specialized knowledge, charisma, wisdom, competence, aptitude, etc., it is usually known as *an authority*. Hence, it is right to say that he/she is an authority in scripture, philosophy, spirituality, guidance, etc. It refers to the exercise of authority due to specialization or

³ David J. Stagaman, *Authority in the Church* (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 1999), 39.

possession of special or unique skills. However, when one exercises authority by virtue of one's office, it is usually known as *in authority*. For instance, a police officer stops my vehicle on the road and asks for the needed documents since he is in authority. In general, those who are in authority should be an authority, i.e., an officer should possess needed skills, knowledge, wisdom, charisma, experience, competence, aptitude for the tasks assigned. If he/she is not, his/her integrity will be in question; he/she may lack credibility, and would be ineffective in the long run. An authority and in authority ought to merge well in a person in the exercise of an office. In authority should demonstrate an authority.⁴

4. AUTHORITY & POWER

Often distinction is made between authority and power. Richard Gaillardetz defines power as "the capacity for effective action" and authority as "the legitimate, trustworthy, and accountable exercise of power."⁵ From this viewpoint, one can have power without authority. For instance, a tyrant can exercise power without having legitimate authority. The same power can become authority when it is exercised legitimately, trustworthily, and accountably. The ecclesial power, when it meets these criteria, can become "capacity to engage in effective action in service of the Church's life and mission."⁶ In good many instances, the exercise of authority would require real power, whether political, economic, technological, academic, or cognitive. A Member of the Parliament or a Member of a Legislative Assembly would achieve very little without the political and economic power. All the same, as defined above in terms of standing/position, there can be authority without power. The obvious examples from history are Mahatma Gandhi, Nelson Mandela, Martin

⁴ Cf. Richard R. Gaillardetz, *By What Authority? Foundations for Understanding Authority in the Church* (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 2018), 13-14.

⁵ Gaillardetz, *By What Authority?*, 4.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 4

Luther King, etc. They exercised authority legitimately, trustworthily, and accountably without any power.

Sandra Schneiders, a Catholic biblical theologian, provides a nuance in her understanding of the terms power and authority. As paraphrased by Gaillardetz, for Schneiders, “power simply as the capacity to move or influence oneself or others ‘either physically or spiritually.’ ... power is essentially neutral. It can be exercised coercively (‘power over’) or in a way that empowers and enables others (‘power for’). ... authority as ‘persuasive power’.”⁷

While Max Weber sees authority as simply ‘legitimate power’ legitimated in traditional authority, legal-rational authority and in charismatic authority, Joseph Komonchak characterizes authority not just as legitimate power but as ‘trustworthy power’ established in multiple ways, namely through goodwill, trust, competency.⁸ Accountability exhibited in openness/transparency can establish trustworthiness.

5. SOURCES OF AUTHORITY IN THE CHURCH

In general, in the scriptures, the source of authority in the Church is the triune God. In the NT, more specifically, Jesus is the supreme authority⁹ and exercises the Father’s authority in his ministry. For instance, in Mt 28:18 he says, “All authority in heaven and on earth has been given to me.” From the authority derived from the Father, he sends out his disciples. From Jesus, the apostles exercise their authority. The apostles were commissioned by Jesus to be his witnesses and to proclaim the Good news. Christ is the head and the Church is his body, and all authority exercised in the Church flows from this relationship with him.¹⁰

In the Gospels, two Greek words, *exousia* and *dynamis*, are used. The former means authority and the latter means

⁷ Ibid., 8.

⁸ As paraphrased in Gaillardetz, *By What Authority?*, 12-13.

⁹ Cf. John L. Mckenzie, *Authority in the Church* (Image Books, 1971), 121.

¹⁰ Cf. *ibid.*, 22-23.

power. The term *dynamis* is used when Jesus uses his power to perform miracles, to heal the sick, and to forgive sinners. The same word is used when Jesus promised that his disciples would receive power that comes from the Holy Spirit (Acts 1:8). St. Paul too uses the same word saying that the work of reconciliation is accomplished through the power of the Spirit (2 Cor 5:18).¹¹ *Exousia* in general is attributed to Jesus' word, to his teaching. "He taught as one who had authority, and not as their teachers of the law" (Mt 7:29; Mk 1:22; Lk 4:32). The question is raised about the authority of Jesus, i.e., by what authority does he teach (Mt 21:23; Mk 11:28; Lk 20:2). *Exousia* in these passages signifies that Jesus has a commission to teach and the source of his authority to teach is the Father. In John's Gospel (5:26-47; 7:16-31) this is still clearer; Jesus speaks and acts by a commission which he has received from the Father. The authority of Jesus is received. He is the spokesperson of the Father.

In addition to the God revealed in Jesus Christ and transmitted to us in the scripture, the scripture – written records / witness to Christ-event of the apostles and the early Christian community – itself is the source of authority for the Church.¹² The apostles are the ones who saw, heard, and touched (1 Jn 1:1) and wrote the scriptures down and they are true (Jn 21:24). They are the evidence of what was believed in the early Church and witness to that faith. They are the product of the faith community inspired by the Holy Spirit (*Dei Verbum*, no. 11) and not of sheer human work. In short, the scripture is God's words in human words.

Since the Church is a community born of the outpouring of the Holy Spirit, the Holy Spirit cannot be excluded but be mentioned while discussing the authority in the Church. The Holy Spirit dwells in and guides and leads the Church (Jn 20:19-23; Acts 2:1-4). The source of exercise of authority

¹¹ Cf. Gaillardetz, *By What Authority?*, 5. Cf. also Stagaman, *Authority in the Church*, 65.

¹² Cf. Gaillardetz, *By What Authority?*, 50-64.

in the Church owes to the presence of the Holy Spirit. The Church transmits what has been handed on by the apostles (*Dei Verbum*, no. 8).

The apostles not only witnessed and transmitted the Christ-event and the scriptures as the source of authority in the Church but are also the source of authority because they were administrators and ministers of the nascent churches. They were sent by Jesus as the Father had sent him (Jn 20:21) and were to go and make disciples of all the nations (Mt 28:19-20) and to be fishers of men and women. They exercised authority derived from Jesus over the faith-communities.¹³ They monitored the life and governance in the Church.¹⁴ Today's administrative authority (on judicial and legislative matters) in the Church has its origin in the apostles, for they are the rock on which the Church is built and have the power to bind and loose. For this same reason, Paul visits Jerusalem to resolve the issue of circumcision and dietary practices that arose in the early Church.

Today, the Bishops – the successors of apostles, spiritual leaders, preachers of the apostolic teachings, presidents of the worshipping assembly¹⁵ – derive and exercise the same authority of the apostles. Today, as apostles, they command the faithful, exhort, lead, guide, and pass on what they have received from the apostles (apostolicity).¹⁶

The sources of the Church's authority also come from the expertise, namely the Magisterium, the Biblical Scholars, and theologians. Their teaching and opinion carry weight.

In sum, the general understanding in the Church of the source of authority is God or Christ. Christ brings the Church into being and sends the Church on mission. The members of the Catholic Church have been urged to see Christ in the

¹³ Cf. Mckenzie, *Authority in the Church*, 43.

¹⁴ Cf. Lacey, *Authority in the Church*, 55.

¹⁵ Cf. Stagaman, *Authority in the Church*, 75.

¹⁶ Cf. Seán Mac Réamoinn (ed.), *Authority in the Church* (Dublin: The Columba Press, 1995), 31. Also cf. Lacey, *Authority in the Church*, 51-67.

officers of the Church and the will of God in their commands. The authority of the officers in the Church is Christ's own ruling authority, bestowed upon the officers. The Pope is the Vicar of Christ. The subjects are to see Christ in their superiors.

The authority within the Church does not originate from the people, as in democratic systems – 'by the people, for the people, of the people.' Nor is it rooted in aristocratic lineage, noble heritage, or royal decree. It also differs from Max Weber's concept of traditional authority, which is grounded in societal customs, founding myths, and long-standing practices. Instead, the Church authority is anchored in divine revelation and sacred tradition: in proclamations such as 'Thus says the Lord,' 'It was said... but I tell you,' 'As the Scriptures say,' and 'According to the teachings of the Church and the Catechism of the Catholic Church.' This foundation is deeply theological and doctrinal, and as such, it remains largely resistant to change.

6. TYPES OF AUTHORITY IN THE CHURCH

The types of authority mentioned below have evolved over time and were not initially present in the NT.¹⁷

Official Authority comes from the office one holds and is exercised when one is empowered by the hierarchy to be at the service of God's people.¹⁸ A bishop exercises his authority because of his office. A parish priest does so for the same reason. It is like any other office in the secular domain. They assume office one day and on some other day relinquish it. The offices are within a well-defined structure in an organization. Certain structure/procedure marks the lifestyle. For example, in the hierarchy in the Church, there is clarity, order, discipline, strong sense of identity, permanence. The official authority has definite boundary/limits for its operation. For instance, the bishop will not go and inspect/supervise some government's electricity work or drainage cleaning work.

¹⁷ Cf. Mckenzie, *Authority in the Church*, 17.

¹⁸ Cf. Réamoinn, *Authority in the Church*, 31.

Charismatic authority is a spontaneous authority and arises according to the need of a particular situation. The convocation of Vatican II by Pope John XXIII can be seen as an example of charismatic authority. Reading the signs of the times in the changing world, Pope John XXIII called for *aggiornamento*. Mahatma Gandhi's authority too was a charismatic authority that arose out of a particular need of freedom from colonialism. Charismatic authority is a type of authority, which calls the Church to live the Gospel, and calls for renewal. We may also make a mention of St. Francis of Assisi. The charismatic authority is something original. It brings forth that which was not there before or was forgotten. In the Church, charismatic authority springs from the inspiration of the Holy Spirit.¹⁹

How to discern charismatic authority? By and large, discerning charismatic authority is done by examining what is said is in harmony with the Christian faith and morals and the teachings of the Church. Any charismatic authority that discredits faith and morals of the Church cannot be true charismatic authority. It has to be in consonance with the Gospel.

The charismatic authority usually encounters opposition, resistance from the hierarchy or from others, for, it generally belongs outside the structures of the official authority. The official authority feels that because of the charismatic authority the existing authority has been threatened and endangered.

The prominent feature of the charismatic authority is that it overcomes stagnation, decay, indolence. It reminds the institution of the original charism. For Max Weber, the charismatic authority is legitimated by the distinctive gifts of an individual or a group of individuals that make them heroic or exemplary in some way. This may be true of charismatic authority in the Church too.

¹⁹ Cf. Gaillardetz, *By What Authority?*, 12.

Moral authority is authority that is born of one's personal integrity and of one's edifying behaviour or a behaviour that conforms to high moral standards.²⁰ A Church leader involved in scandals of various types cannot have moral authority. He/she will have no moral authority over the community called the Church. 1 Tim 3:1-7; Tit 1:5-9; 1 Tim 3:8-13 speak of personal integrity and edifying behaviour of bishops and deacons.

Teaching authority in the Church, assisted by the Holy Spirit, is vested in the Magisterium.²¹ It concentrates on the teachings of the Church. Formal in its viewpoints, the magisterial authority exhorts, explicates the teachings of the Church, and calls for obedience for the promotion of unity of faith. It believes that it is the guardian of the deposit of faith and its transmission. It is responsible for authentically interpreting the Word of God, whether in the written form (Sacred Scripture) or in the oral form (Sacred tradition). In exercising its authority, its task is to interpret and preserve the Truth passed on to us by the Apostles. It prevents the possible deviations in faith.

The Church requires a teaching authority because the human spirit can often misinterpret and misconstrue the meaning of the Scriptures and elements of faith and morals derived from the scriptures.²² Thus, the vulnerabilities of the human spirit need a teaching authority which bears the special charge of fidelity to the tradition and harmony with living faith, of guiding the community to lead a life worthy of Christian calling in belief and practice. In other words, the purpose of teaching authority is to instruct the faithful concerning the right belief and right praxis.

Legal Authority is the authority that flows from the exercising of laws – prudent conclusions that the Church

²⁰ Cf. McKenzie, *Authority in the Church*, 11-12

²¹ Cf. R. R. Gaillardetz, *Teaching with Authority: A Theology of the Magisterium in the Church* (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 1997), 131-189

²² Cf. Stagaman, *Authority in the Church*, 125.

has drawn from the past and its forethought for facing the future responsibly – evolved over centuries to safeguard and to ensure fidelity to Christian life and practice in the Church. Basically, it is exercised by the canon lawyers in the Church. Legal authority is necessary in the Church for better and efficient functioning, maintaining order, and to bear witness to the Gospel values. In short, legal authority is exercised through directives/guidelines for temporal and moral life. The focus is on the letter of the law, clarity and precision, removing vagueness and ambiguity. In its viewpoint, it is formal. It concerns itself with procedural proprieties and questions of boundaries (who belongs and who doesn't). For Max Weber, this is legal-rational authority; it depends on accepted rules and conventions. In the Church, it may be said that it is manifested in the bureaucratized activity of the Roman curia and the application of canon law at all levels of ecclesial life.²³

Pastoral authority, which is spiritual, ethical, and moral in nature, is typically embodied by devout men and women whose lives reflect godliness. This form of leadership is deeply concerned with nurturing faith, shaping moral character, and cultivating the spiritual vitality of communities through teaching, exhortation, and catechesis. St. Paul, in his epistles, emphasizes the gifts bestowed by the Holy Spirit for the edification of the body of Christ—gifts intended for the spiritual, ethical, and moral formation of believers (cf. 1 Cor 12:4-11; 12:28-31). Theologian Yves Congar highlights that the spiritual essence of ecclesial authority is especially evident in two formative periods of Church history: the era of the martyrs (from the apostolic age to Constantine) and the age of monastic Christianity (from the fourth century to the mid-eleventh century). During these times, spiritual authority was reserved for those recognized as ‘men and women of God’—individuals whose lives were marked by

²³ Cf. Gaillardetz, *By What Authority*, 12.

spiritual depth and vitality. In the early Church, bishops and leaders were distinguished not merely by office but by their spiritual endowment—graced with the gifts of the Spirit to guide the faithful.²⁴ If the Church's mission is to foster spiritual maturity among its members, then only those who are spiritually alive are deemed fit to exercise such authority.

Administrative authority is about day-to-day governance of the Church, local and global, or running of the Church. This authority looks after things so that everything flows smoothly without confusion, and there is no chaos. The Roman curia exercises the administrative authority with its bishops, and the bishops exercise with their priests. The evolved structures or well-laid down norms or skilled personnel facilitate the exercise of administrative authority.²⁵ The hierarchy in the Church and the authority it exercises is an example of administrative authority (the Pope, Bishops, college of bishops, diocese, deanery, parishes, parish zones).

In all types of authority, the Church believes that the Spirit of God is present and guides everyone. The authority in the Church may sometimes manifest in disciplinary action. Some opine that it is medicinal and not punitive. Others believe that it is never appropriate. Some others say that it is needed to preserve good order in the community, to guard the apostolic faith.

7. BLESSING: A VISION FOR THE EXERCISE OF AUTHORITY

Before we proceed to speak of the vision and relate it to blessing, we wish to highlight Victor Lee Austin's understanding of authority. For Victor Lee Austin, "Authority is built into what it means to be human, and we never will escape from needing it for our flourishing."²⁶ He makes a distinction between substitutionary and non-substitutionary forms of authority.

²⁴ Cf. Meneo A. Afonso, *What is the Nature of Authority in the Church* (Lanham, MD: University Press of America, 1996), 62.

²⁵ Cf. Mckenzie, *Authority in the Church*, 106.

²⁶ Cited in Gaillardetz, *By What Authority?*, 9-10.

Substitutionary & Non-substitutionary authority: The substitutionary authority is evident in the parental exercise of authority. The parent's authority fills for (substitutes for) some lack of maturity or experience in the child. The parent tells a young child not to cross a street because the child is incapable of making such a judgment for itself. Substitutionary authority compensates for a fundamental lack in the person subject to that authority. It also functions a corrective against some defect in the other. One assumes that as the person grows and matures, the substitutionary authority would diminish.

Non-substitutionary authority is about coordinating activities of the individuals/communities for the sake of the realization of a vision. It focuses on tapping all gifts and abilities and making most out of it for a vision. The example given here is the authority of an orchestra conductor who exercises his/her authority to maximize the individual gifts of the musicians in order to produce a wonderful symphony. All the members of an orchestra are to will the wonderful overall outcome/performance and they are to be concerned with their specific duty to perform those parts of the composition assigned to their particular instruments. The conductor is concerned with both – the outcome and the individual performance. Similarly, we can think of the example of the Vice-chancellor and the professors in a university. The Vice-chancellor directs and oversees the life and activities of the university according to its vision. The professors, in their capacities, are committed to the university's vision and dedicate their services to realize the same vision through their work. This is just to point out that non-substitutionary authority is concerned with the realization of a vision by bringing out the best through facilitation and coordination. This is in harmony with what Paul teaches about the 'One Spirit, many gifts'; hierarchical and charismatic gifts, ministries and charisms (1 Cor 12:4, LG 4).²⁷

²⁷ Paraphrased in Gaillardetz, *By What Authority?*, 10.

Vision: In general, vision can be considered as an imagined, thought/planned out future. A vision can be imposed by another party, a self-designed vision by an individual or a group of individuals/community. Vision unites a community. A community agrees on it and works together to realize it.

Vision, when humanly designed or has its origin in humans, can be called an ideology, i.e., a product of human thinking, e.g., communism, humanism, welfarism. However, in the religious realm, vision is a product of God's revelation and cannot be a product of human design. The vision that we refer to here is the biblical vision of new creation or 'new heavens and new earth' (2 Pet 3:13; Rev 21:1; Isa 65:17; 66:22). Clearly, therefore, it is not a vision of 'liberty, equality, fraternity' of the French revolution and an 'egalitarian society' of Marx, or a vision imagined in the preamble of any nation's constitution or any other ideology. The vision that we are referring to is God revealed vision in the Bible. The Church moves toward this eschatological vision ever accompanied by the Holy Spirit.

The eschatological vision revealed in the New Testament was actually a reality already present after God had brought forth creation and had blessed it. God's 'heavens and earth' at the time of creation were impeccable and perfect as the 'new heavens and new earth' will be, until the sin entered the creation. God created everything and found everything that God had created as 'good' (Gen 1).

Blessing: In the book of Genesis, the theme of blessing – an all-pervading theme in the Bible – is prominent. Even a casual reading of the Book of Genesis reveals the prominence of the theme of blessing. In the creation account itself, the term 'blessing' is repeated four times. The work of creation is wrapped in the divine blessing: Animal life (1:22), human life (1:28), and the seventh day (2:3) are all blessed specifically.

Blessing is a divine act. Insofar as the narration in the creation account goes, God ‘said’ and it was, and God ‘saw’ that it was ‘good.’ And God ‘blessed.’ To put it differently, God uttered what was in God’s mind and it came into being, viewed it and felt it as good and then blessed it. God’s blessing, therefore, is an action that expressed and confirmed the correspondence between the external creation and God’s mind and heart. What really was in God’s mind and heart that took expression in outward creation and received God’s blessing. A closer reading of the creation narrative tells us that it was about fullness, goodness, life, light, sanctity, and bond. God blessed these realities from the inception of God’s creation itself.²⁸ Blessing, therefore, is God’s act of confirmation of the created reality that God envisaged and becomes God-revealed eschatological vision, namely ‘new heavens and new earth’ later when the original ‘heavens and earth’ did not remain as God wished it to be. Blessing represents God’s original vision of creation or creation in its original state about which God felt ‘Good.’

8. SIN: DISRUPTION OF BLESSING

Sin is a reality and represents actions opposed to the divine act of blessing; everything that does not express and confirm to God’s mind and heart; it is all that is opposed to or destroys fullness, goodness, light, life, bond, and sanctity; it is something that disrupts the perfect correspondence that existed between God’s mind and heart and his creation. Sin is staying away from blessing. In creating, God saw everything as ‘good,’ but in sin narratives (sin of Adam & Eve, Cain murdering Abel, the Flood, Tower of Babel, Sodom & Gomorrah), we read that God sees everything that does not correspond to ‘good.’²⁹

28 Cf. Lancy Monteiro, “Mission: Blessing the Blessing,” *VJTR* 89/10 (Oct 2025): 742-756 and *VJTR* 89/11 (Nov 2025): 808-818.

29 Cf. Jeff S. Anderson, *The Blessing and the Curse: Trajectories in the Theology of the Old Testament* (Eugene, OR: Cascade Books, 2014), 85.

It begins with Adam's disobedience and continues in sin narratives in Genesis.

9. CHRIST-CHURCH: RESTORER-SACRAMENT OF BLESSING

Jesus, the Son of God, incarnates to restore God's original blessing. He is light (Jn 8:12), life (Jn 11:25), bond between God and humanity (Jn 1:14), fullness (Col 2:9), visible image of the invisible God (Col 1:15), radiance of God's glory and the exact imprint of God's nature (Heb 1:3), perfect good without sin and evil (Heb 4:15). In other words, Jesus is God's mind and heart in flesh. Furthermore, he is not only God's mind and heart enfleshed, but also the restorer of God's creation to its original status or to the revealed eschatological vision that we mentioned earlier. 'All things will be subjected to him; he himself will be subjected to God who put all things in subjection under him, that God may be all in all (1 Cor 15:28).

The Church, Christ's body and sacrament, cannot be different from what Christ was³⁰ and what he came to accomplish, i.e., God's mind and heart, and the mission of restoration of creation to its original state. The Church, therefore, pursues to be Christ's mind and heart in the world in Christ's mission of restoration through her life and actions, which are becoming a channel of blessing in the realization of eschatological vision of 'new heavens and new earth.'

Authority, when exercised in the pursuit of this noble vision, holds the potential to manifest a heaven on earth. This potential reaches its fullest expression when authority aligns with the God-revealed eschatological vision of the 'new heavens and new earth'—a restoration of creation to its divinely blessed original state. In the life of the Church, every form of authority – be it legal, administrative, moral, doctrinal, pastoral, spiritual, or charismatic – is called to serve this sacred purpose. All exercise of authority in the Church,

³⁰ Cf. McKenzie, *Authority in the Church*, 23.

therefore, in whichever domain – legal, administrative, moral, teaching, pastoral/spiritual, or charismatic – can be understood to serve³¹ this purpose. Christ-given authority in the Church is to restore what God had confirmed in the act of blessing or to serve the revealed eschatological vision. The Church – the pilgrim people of God, the body of Christ, the temple of the Holy Spirit – exercises her authority for the realization of this vision or restore ‘heavens and earth’ that was blessed by God. Misappropriation of authority occurs when the use of authority strays from the realization of the eschatological vision and is used for control, coercion, domination, bullying, silencing, for lording it over (Mt 20:25), for serving self and vested interests. When words and actions of authorities promote fullness, life, light, good, bond, sanctity, the eschatological vision becomes tangible. Like conductors of a great orchestra, Church authorities bring harmony to diverse voices and gifts, guiding them toward the restoration of God’s original blessing on creation.

CONCLUSION

This article was an attempt to understand what authority is and all its nuances. Thus, we saw authority as something one exercises because of one’s standing in the society and also as binding interaction. We also distinguished what is ‘an authority and in authority’ and ‘authority and power.’ The discussion also informed us of the sources and kinds of authority in the Church. The exercise of authority must be guided by a vision. To wield authority meaningfully, one must anchor it in a vision; otherwise, it drifts toward self-interest. God-revealed eschatological vision, namely ‘new heavens and new earth’ – already present at the inception of creation and which corresponded to God’s mind and heart and which God confirmed in the act of blessing – could be the vision guiding the exercise of authority in the Church.

³¹ Cf. *ibid.*, 81.